

An Observation Study Assessing the Knowledge on PCOS among AdolescentsNaaz Ahmed¹, Vinita Sahay²¹Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Netaji Subhas Medical College, Bihta, Patna, India²Professor and HOD, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Netaji Subhas Medical College, Bihta, Patna, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Naaz Ahmed

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Aim:** The aim of the present study was to assess the knowledge on PCOS among adolescents.**Methods:** The present study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Netaji Subhas Medical College, Bihta, Patna, India and 200 adolescents was included in the study.**Results:** In present study, 60% girls were young girls in the age group of 20-24 years while 40% girls were adolescent girls in the group of 18-19 years. In present study, 50% girls had normal BMI, 20% were overweight, 16% were obese while 14% were underweight. In present study, 52% girls were consuming pure vegetarian diet while 48% girls were consuming mixed (vegetarian and non-vegetarian) food. In present study, 35% girls had acne, 17% had irregularity of menses, 5% had hirsutism. Hormonal profile for hyperandrogenism was suggested. In present study, 34% adolescent and young girls had information about PCOS from teacher, 19% got information from friend, 12% got information from a doctor, 3% got information from newspaper while 6% got information from internet. 27% adolescent and young girls were unaware of PCOS. In this study, 10% girls consulted dermatologist for either hirsutism or acne, 5% consulted gynaecologist for irregularity of menses, 1% girls sought ayurvedic treatment while 1% opted for homeopathy. Amongst 17% girls who consulted a doctor, 10% girls did ultrasonography and blood investigations. Amongst them, 5% girls were diagnosed as having PCOS. So, prevalence of PCOS in present study was 5%.**Conclusion:** Prevalence of PCOS in present study was 5%. Most common source of information about PCOS was teacher as the girls were medical students. Girls who were having BMI more than 23 should be educated about its hazards and should be advised weight loss. Girls who had irregularity of menses and signs of hyperandrogenism should be investigated and must be managed accordingly. Early diagnosis of PCOS and its prompt treatment will help the girls to improve quality of life and prevent further health hazards.**Keywords:** Adolescent girls, BMI, PCOS

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Introduction

Polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) is one of the most common reproductive endocrine logical disorders with a broad spectrum of clinical manifestations affecting about 6-8% of women of reproductive years. [1] The diverse manifestations of PCOS start at an early age when a girls maturing into a young woman. During this pubertal transition, several features may be in evolution and thus many findings may be transitory which stabilize later during adolescence. However, it is important to make an early diagnosis in order to prevent early and late sequel of the syndrome.

PCOS a diagnosis of exclusion has been a topic of debate and many consensus definitions have

evolved over time. The National Institute for Health (NIH) Criteria 1990 was revised in 2003 and Rotterdam criteria [2] has been adopted world over. However, recently in 2006, Androgen Excess Society (AES) has come up with a consensus statement, defining PCOS as a hyper androgenic state and emphasises the presence of either clinical and/ or biochemical features of hyper androgenism along with other features of PCOS for diagnosis. [3] Globally, prevalence estimates of PCOS are highly variable, ranging from 2.2% to as high as 26%. [4-8] Community-based studies using Rotterdam criteria among reproductive age group women have demonstrated varied prevalence

figures in few Asian countries ranging from 2% to 7.5% in China [9-10] to 6.3% in Sri Lanka. [11]

Studies among several Caucasian populations using NIH criteria reported PCOS in the range of 5-8%. [4-12] An Australian retrospective birth cohort study of 728 women reported a prevalence of $11.9 \pm 2.4\%$ as per Rotterdam criteria, which increased to $17.8 \pm 2.8\%$ when imputed data were included. Under the AES recommendations, PCOS prevalence was $10.2 \pm 2.2\%$, and $12.0 \pm 2.4\%$ with the imputed data. [13] Although there are limited studies of PCOS in India, the observational studies by endocrinologists, gynecologists, and dermatologists relate to diverse aspects of PCOS. Prevalence of obesity and diabetes mellitus in most industrialized countries including India is also on the rise owing to urbanization and change in lifestyle. Most of the young population does not visit health facilities until they have late sequel of the problem. Most prevalence studies in India are in hospital set-ups and recently a few studies among adolescents in schools report prevalence of PCOS as 9.13% to 36%. [14-15]

The aim of the present study was to assess the knowledge on PCOS among adolescents.

Materials and Methods

The present study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Netaji Subhas Medical College, Bihta, Patna, India for 1 year and 200 adolescents was included in the study.

The data was collected by using structured knowledge questionnaire on PCOS. The

investigator obtained permission from the students, prior to the data collection and assured confidentiality to the subject to get their cooperation and explained the purpose of the study. The results were analyzed.

Data Collection was as follows:

- Age
- Weight in kg and height in cm to calculate BMI
- Type of diet- Vegetarian or mixed diet
- Irregularity of menses
- Signs of hyperandrogenism-Hirsutism or acne
- Source of information-Teacher, doctor, friend, paper or internet
- Type of consultation-Dermatologist or gynaecologist or any other
- No. of diagnosed case

Operational definitions

- Adolescent girls- 10-19 years (for present study 18- 19 years).
- Young girls- 20-24 years.
- Body mass index-

Normal: BMI =18-22.9 kg/m², Underweight: BMI <17.9 kg/m², Overweight: BMI >23 kg/m²,

Obese: BMI >25 kg/m² for girls above 18 years

Results

Table 1: Baseline characteristics

Age group	No. of patients	Percent
18-19 years	80	40
20-24 years	120	60
BMI		
<17.9 kg/m ² underweight	28	14
18-22.9 kg/m ² normal	100	50
>23 kg/m ² overweigh	40	20
>25 kg/m ² obese	32	16
Type of diet		
Mixed (veg and non-veg)	96	48
Vegetarian	104	52
Problems		
Irregularity of menses	34	17
Hirsutism	12	6
Acne	70	35

In present study, 60% girls were young girls in the age group of 20-24 years while 40% girls were adolescent girls in the group of 18-19 years. In present study, 50% girls had normal BMI, 20% were overweight, 16% were obese while 14% were underweight. In present study, 52% girls were

consuming pure vegetarian diet while 48% girls were consuming mixed (vegetarian and non-vegetarian) food. In present study, 35% girls had acne, 17% had irregularity of menses, 5% had hirsutism. Hormonal profile for hyperandrogenism was suggested.

Table 2: Source of information about PCOS

Source of information about PCOS	No. of patients	Percent
Teacher	68	34
Friend	36	18
Doctor	24	12
Paper	6	3
Internet	12	6
No information	54	27

In present study, 34% adolescent and young girls had information about PCOS from teacher, 19% got information from friend, 12% got information from a doctor, 3% got information from newspaper while 6% got information from internet. 27% adolescent and young girls were unaware of PCOS.

Table 3: Type of doctor attended and Prevalence of PCOS

Type of doctor attended	No. of girls	Percent
Dermatologist	20	10
Gynaecologist	10	5
Ayurvedic	2	1
Homeopathic	2	1
Prevalence		
Consultation with doctor	34	17
Investigations done	20	10
Proved PCOS	10	5

In this study, 10% girls consulted dermatologist for either hirsutism or acne, 5% consulted gynaecologist for irregularity of menses, 1% girls sought ayurvedic treatment while 1% opted for homeopathy. Amongst 17% girls who consulted a doctor, 10% girls did ultrasonography and blood investigations. Amongst them, 5% girls were diagnosed as having PCOS. So, prevalence of PCOS in present study was 5%.

Discussion

Polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) is a condition in which woman has an imbalance of female sex hormones. This may lead to changes in the menstrual cycle, cyst in the ovary, failure to conceive and other health problems. It is a common health problem among teenagers and young women. It affects 5% to 10% of women in their reproductive years. These problems cause infertility. Research has suggested that PCOS may be related to increased insulin production. PCOS seems to run in families, too, so if someone in the family has it, they might be more likely to develop it. [16]

The prevalence has been increasing in the adolescent population. [17] In more than 40% of cases, PCOS is associated with obesity, as well as impaired glucose tolerance, type 2 diabetes, and the metabolic syndrome. [18] While the pathophysiology of PCOS remains unclear, insulin resistance has been implicated as a major causative factor.¹⁹ Accurate diagnosis of PCOS is of critical importance to public health, given the chronic nature of the disorder and its association with multiple health consequences. [18] In present

study, 60% girls were young girls in the age group of 20-24 years while 40% girls were adolescent girls in the group of 18-19 years. The diverse manifestations of PCOS start at an early age when a girl is maturing into a young woman. it is important to make an early diagnosis in order to prevent early and late sequel of the syndrome. [20] Sunanda B et al [16] revealed that 85% of the samples were in the age group of 21-25 years, 75% of the samples were Christians, 82% of the samples were consuming mixed diet, and 92% samples had regular menstrual cycle. In present study, 50% girls had normal BMI, 20% were overweight, 16% were obese while 14% were underweight. Sanchez N et al [19] found that 32% were obese. Overweight and obese girls are more prone for PCOS. Counselling was given and weight reduction was advised. Also, hormonal profile for thyroid, hyperandrogenism was suggested. In present study, 52% girls were consuming pure vegetarian diet while 48% girls were consuming mixed (vegetarian and non-vegetarian) food. Advice regarding healthy food was given. In present study, 60% girls were young girls in the age group of 20-24 years while 40% girls were adolescent girls in the group of 18-19 years. In present study, 50% girls had normal BMI, 20% were overweight, 16% were obese while 14% were underweight. In present study, 52% girls were consuming pure vegetarian diet while 48% girls were consuming mixed (vegetarian and non-vegetarian) food. In present study, 35% girls had acne, 17% had irregularity of menses, 5% had hirsutism. Hormonal profile for hyperandrogenism was suggested. Joshi et al²⁰ found that history of oligomenorrhea had a positive predictive value of

93.3% and negative predictive value of 86.7% to detect a possible case of PCOS.

In present study, 34% adolescent and young girls had information about PCOS from teacher, 19% got information from friend, 12% got information from a doctor, 3% got information from newspaper while 6% got information from internet. 27% adolescent and young girls were unaware of PCOS. Sills ES et al found that more than 97% (n =638) of the respondents were familiar with PCOS, while 1.9% had not been told about PCOS, and <1% were uncertain.¹⁷ In this study, 10% girls consulted dermatologist for either hirsutism or acne, 5% consulted gynaecologist for irregularity of menses, 1% girls sought ayurvedic treatment while 1% opted for homeopathy. Amongst 17% girls who consulted a doctor, 10% girls did ultrasonography and blood investigations. Amongst them, 5% girls were diagnosed as having PCOS. So, prevalence of PCOS in present study was 5%. Shetty D found that around 10% of Indian women are affected with Polycystic Ovary Syndrome, commonly known as PCOS. [21] Choudhary N et al found that prevalence of PCOS in Indian adolescents is 9.13%. [22] Vaidya R et al found that according to World Health Organization, there are PCOS affected 116 million women worldwide in 2012 (3.4% of women). [23] Lakshmi KS et al found that the prevalence of PCOS at a tertiary care hospital was 32%. [24]

Conclusion

Prevalence of PCOS in present study was 5%. Most common source of information about PCOS was teacher as the girls were medical students. Girls who were having BMI more than 23 should be educated about its hazards and should be advised weight loss. Girls who had irregularity of menses and signs of hyperandrogenism should be investigated and must be managed accordingly. Early diagnosis of PCOS and its prompt treatment will help the girls to improve quality of life and prevent further health hazards. Thorough knowledge of the disorder and counseling for adolescents should be included in the curriculum which will provide awareness towards the disorder and lifestyle modification. Accurate diagnosis at a younger age may be a key.

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